

flagellar evolution

By: Reihaneh Shekari
PhD Student

What is a flagella?

Intruduction

- ▶ A large number of bacteria are motile.
- ▶ Most possess one or more flagella on their surface that allow them to swim.
- ▶ Bacterial flagella are tiny hair.
- ▶ The straight line movement is called a run and the turn is called a tumble.
- ▶ Motility of eukaryotic flagella is deperenedent upon ATPase activity
- ▶ Their fine protein structure requires special staining techniques for demonstrating them with the light microscope.
- ▶ The pattern of flagellation is an important feature in identification of motile bacteria.
- ▶ Flagell have 20 nm and 15-20um Long

Flagel structure

- ▶ About 50 genes are required for flagella synthesis and function.
- ▶ The flagella apparatus consists of several distinct proteins
- ▶ distinct proteins: a system of rings embedded in the cell envelope (the basal body), a hook-like structure near the cell surface, and the flagella filament.

Flagel structure

- ▶ **Transmission electron microscope studies have shown that the bacterial flagellum is composed of three parts:**
- ▶ The longest & most obvious portion is the flagellar filament, which extends from the cell surface to the tip.
- ▶ A basal body is embedded in the cell.
- ▶ A short curved segment, the flagellar hook, links the filament to its basal body & acts as flexible coupling.
- ▶ Flagellin30000-60000 Dalton
- ▶ Tip in end

Flagel structure

- ▶ The innermost rings, the **M and S** rings, located in the plasma membrane, comprise the motor apparatus.
- ▶ The outermost rings, the **P and L** rings, located in the periplasme and the outer membrane respectively, function as bushings to support the rod.
- ▶ Geram Negative all of 4 ring but geram positive have S and M ring

Chemical composition

- ▶ Protein-70-81%
- ▶ Lipid-13-23%
- ▶ Carbohydrate-1-6%

Types of flagella

DIVISION OF BACTERIA ON THE BASIS OF PRESENCE OF FLAGELLA

MONOTRICOUS

CEPHALOTRICOUS

AMPHITRICOUS

PERITRICOUS

LOPHOTRICOUS

ATRICOUS

- ▶ **MONOTRICHOUS:** Bacteria have one flagellum if it is located at & end it is said to be a polar flagellum .
- ▶ Ex –pseudomonas V, cholera
- ▶ **LOPHOTRICHOUS :** Bacteria have a cluster of flagella at one or both ends
- ▶ Ex-spirillum,
- ▶ **PERITRICHOUS:** Flagella are spread fairly evenly over the whole surface of Peritrichous bacteria.
- ▶ Ex Proteins vulgaris
- ▶ Cephalotrichous
- ▶ Atrichuos

- ▶ The synthesis of bacterial flagella is a complex process involving at least 20-30 genes
- ▶ Besides the gene for flagellin, 10 or more genes code for hook & basal body proteins, other genes are concerned with the control of flagella construction or function.
- ▶ Transport of many flagellar components is carried out by an apparatus in the basal body that is a specialized type III protein secretion system.
- ▶ Many structures form spontaneously through the association of their component parts without the aid of any special enzymes or other factors.
- ▶ Blast Technique by Ochoa $\dots\dots$ FliG, FliM, FliI, FliC

Mechanism of movement with flagella

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- ▶ The Flagler motor converts electrochemical energy into torque by interacting between two components: the stator and the rotor.
- ▶ The stator consists of two proteins with several versions, including MotA and MotB.
- ▶ They accumulate in a structure associated with the inner membrane and attach to peptidoglycan.
- ▶ MotA-MotB acts as a proton channel
- ▶ Wheel-like rotors include several FliG versions, which together with FliM and FliN form the C-ring

- ▶ Flagellae vary in shape, some are flexible and some are non-flexible
- ▶ Some are linear and some are twisted. Some undergo post-translational changes, such as methylation and glycosylation, and some, Do not.
- ▶ The flagella can be very diverse, but we have to admit that all of these flagella evolved from a common ancestor.

Salmonella

~1260 pN nm

Vibrio

~2200 pN nm

Campylobacter

~3600 pN nm

The role of Tip in assembly Filament

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- ▶ single filament can consist of more than twenty thousand subunits.
- ▶ It can be repaired
- ▶ It has selective performance capability

- ▶ So far, two types of engines have been identified based on ionic, sodium, and hydrogen types
- ▶ Many mobile bacteria include, *B. subtilis*, *S. typhimurium*, *E. coli* *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and, *R. sphaeroides* have a hydrogen ion-dependent flagellar motor
- ▶ *V. alginolyticus*, and alkaline alloys have a sodium-dependent

Transfer torque from the motor to the rotor

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- ▶ FliG and FliN proteins make FliM a switch structure that is important in the production of rotation, assembly, and rotation change.
- ▶ Studies have shown that the 46-N terminal domain of FliG protein is essential for interacting with FliF and transmitting torque, so that these proteins are linked in equal proportions, one by one.

Other Flagella Roll

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- ▶ The flagellar research community received a surprise two years ago from a downsized relative of *Escherichia coli*, the aphid endosymbiont, *Buchnera aphidicola*. Although nonmotile, this intracellular bacterium possesses all the genes necessary for hook–basal–body biosynthesis, although it lacks any of the genes for filament assembly, including the gene for flagellin. In late 2006, a group of Japanese researchers showed that the *Buchnera* cell surface is studded with hundreds of hook–basal–body complexes. These remarkable structures provide a glimpse of a cut-down flagellar system that must have some role other than motility – probably the **export of proteins essential** to the bacteria–aphid symbiotic relationship.
- ▶ *Brucella melitensis* Flagel is involved in **pathogenesis**

Evulation

- ▶ intelligent design' (ID) Beh
- ▶ whether ID is science? NO

ID(intelligent design) theory

- ▶ **irreducible complexity.....FliI**
- ▶ **Flaglar proteins are unique.... Their isn't homologue**

Rejected the unique Flagelle proteins

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- ▶ Nonetheless, similar studies also fuelled unquestioned support in the
- ▶ flagellar research community for an essential role for FliI
- ▶ in early 2008
- ▶ assembly and motility were all possible, even in the absence of FliI
- ▶ mutations in other flagellar components were able to restore near-wildtype capabilities

Reasons for rejecting ID theory

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- ▶ Homology of flagellar proteins with other proteins
- ▶ Rejected bi unique Flagelle proteins

Hemology of flagellar proteins with other proteins

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- ▶ The MotA–MotB and FliM–FliN proteins have obvious homologues outside the flagellum
- ▶ FliG
- ▶ MgtE family
- ▶ In 2007, crystallographic structures became available for the cytosolic components of the MgtE proteins of
- ▶ *Thermus thermophilus* and *Enterococcus faecalis*
- ▶ N-terminal subdomain (the N-domain) forming a right-handed superhelix
- ▶ and a C-terminal subdomain consisting of cystathionine
- ▶ beta synthase (CBS)

Homologies of flagellar proteins

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FliG	Peripheral	Motor	Yes	MgtE [†]
FliH	T3SS apparatus	Regulates FliI	Mutant retains some motility	YscL [*] , AtpFH [†]
FliI	T3SS apparatus	ATPase for protein export	Yes	YscN [†] , AtpD [†] , Rho [†]
FliJ	Cytoplasm	Chaperone	Undetectable in some systems	YscO [†]
FliK	Hook/basal body	Controls hook length	Yes	YscP [†]
FliL	Basal body	Unknown	Mutant retains full motility	None yet known
FliM	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Yes	FliN [†] , YscQ [†]
FliN	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Yes	FliM [†] , YscQ [†]
FliO	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Undetectable in some systems	None
FliP	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Yes	YscR [†]
FliQ	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Yes	YscS [†]
FliR	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Yes	YscT [†]
FliS	Cytoplasm	FliC chaperone	Absent from <i>Caulobacter</i>	None yet known
FliT	Cytoplasm	FliD chaperone	Absent from many systems	None yet known
FliZ	Cytoplasm	Regulator	Absent from many systems	None yet known
MotA	Inner membrane	Motor	Yes	ExbB [†] , TolQ [†]
MotB	Inner membrane	Motor	Yes	ExbD [†] , TolR [†] , OmpA [†]

Homologies of flagellar proteins

Protein	Location	Function	Indispensable?	Homologies*
FlgA	P ring	Chaperone?	Absent from Gram-positive bacteria	CpaB [†]
FlgBCFG	Rod	Transmission shaft	Yes	FlgBCEFGK [§]
FlgD	Hook	Hook cap	Yes	
FlgE	Hook	Universal joint	Yes	FlgBCEFGK
FlgH	L ring	Bushing	Absent from Gram-positive bacteria	None yet known
FlgI	P ring	Bushing	Absent from Gram-positive bacteria	None yet known
FlgJ	Rod	Rod cap; muramidase	FlgJ N-terminal domain absent from some systems	None yet known
FlgK	Hook–filament junction	Hook-associated protein 1	Yes	FlgBCEFGK [§]
FlgL	Hook–filament junction	Hook-associated protein 3	Yes	FliC [§]
FlgM	Cytoplasm and exterior	Anti- σ factor	Absent from <i>Caulobacter</i>	None yet known
FlgN	Cytoplasm	Chaperone	Undetectable in some systems	None yet known
FlhA	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Yes	LcrD/YscV
FlhB	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Yes	YscU
FlhDC	Cytoplasm	Transcriptional regulator	Absent from many systems	Other activators [†]
FlhE	Unknown	Unknown	Mutant retains full motility	
FliA	Cytoplasm	σ factor	Absent from <i>Caulobacter</i>	RpoD, RpoH, RpoS
FliB	Cytoplasm	N-methylase	Absent from <i>Escherichia coli</i>	
FliC	Filament	Flagellin	Yes	FlgL [§] , EspA
FliD	Filament	Filament cap; hook-associated protein 2	Absent from <i>Caulobacter</i>	None yet known
FliE	Rod/basal body	MS ring–rod junction	Yes	None yet known
FliF	T3SS apparatus	Protein export	Yes	YscJ [§]
FliG	Peripheral	Motor	Yes	MgtE

- ▶ **NF- T3SS protein EspA homologos whit Fagel**
- ▶ **S. Typhimurium**
- ▶ **Edwardsiella ictaluri**
- ▶ **Shewanella Baltic**
- ▶ **Chromobacterium violaceum**
- ▶ **Yersinia frederiksenii**
- ▶ **Yersinia bercovieri**
- ▶ **Sodalis glossinidius**

- ▶ Chlamydia is not flagella but It have genomes
- ▶ Myxococcus xanthus is Gliding motility

Probably flagella made from

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- ▶ A secretory system
- ▶ Flament of two ancient proteins
- ▶ Motor from an ion channel
- ▶ And a chemotaxis system in cell

- ▶ For eukaryotes, planktomists refer to fossil record and phylogenetic comparisons.
- ▶ There is no fossil record for molecular machines, which means that evolutionary inferences must be based on sequence.
- ▶ The type 3 secretory system, called the molecular syringe, injects toxins into the eukaryotic cell. It is homologous with stator

- ▶ Notwithstanding the good scientific reasons for new forays in this direction, the lack of a scientific literature on flagellar evolution also has another undesirable consequence — it leaves open the suspicion among members of the public that maybe there is some mystery here, that maybe the ID proponents do have a point.
- ▶ Although all experts agree that there is nothing to these claims, as Wilkins has recently pointed out⁶⁸, in these politically charged times, it is no longer enough to say, for example, that bacterial flagella evolved and that is in this field that. Instead, scientific experts have to engage with a skeptical public.
- ▶ Scott Minnich speculated in his testimony that studies on flagellar evolution need not be restricted to sequence analysis or theoretical models, but that instead this topic could become the subject of laboratory-based experimental studies.

- ▶ **how might such studies be conducted?**
- ▶ One option might be to look back in time
- ▶ An alternative, more radical, option would be to model flagellar evolution prospectively, for example, by creating random or minimally constrained libraries and then iteratively selecting proteins that assemble into ever more sophisticated artificial analogues of the flagellar filament.
- ▶ Another experimental option might be to investigate the environmental conditions that favour or disfavour bacterial motility. The fundamental physics involved (diffusion due to Brownian motion) is mathematically tractable, and has already been used to predict, for example, that powered motility is useless in very small bacteria.

Referance

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THANK YOU
FOR YOUR
ATTENTION